

OSPO-RADAR

Metadata Workshop: Summary Report

March 10, 2026

Project Title	Open Source Program Office Research Assets Dashboard and Archival Resource (link)
Project Acronym	OSPO-RADAR
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Start Date of Project	2025-06-01
Duration of Project	24 months

Work Package	WP2, Project management, specifications, planning, and testing
Authors	Emilie Nguyen Van Yen, Morane Gruenpeter, Renaud Boyer, Linda Angulo Lopez
Participants(s)	Céanne Baccam, Guillaume Bourdat, Julien Coupier, Chris Erdmann, Thomas Hughes, Daniel S. Katz, Violaine Louvet, Emily Lovell, Will Gearty, Virginia Scarlett
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Version	V1.0

Workshop at a Glance

8 participants | 5 absolute priority votes + 8 important + 12 secondary per participant | 47+ properties evaluated

Goal: Identify the most relevant metadata for surfacing in the OSPO-RADAR dashboard, and explore annotation needs for software assets.

1. Workshop Overview

The workshop brought together 8 participants from a mix of roles involved in managing, curating, and using research software. Represented communities included OSPO practitioners, research software engineers, open science practitioners, and metadata and infrastructure stakeholders.

Objectives

The workshop aimed to:

- Improve data consistency, usability, and user workflows in the OSPO-RADAR dashboard
- Produce actionable recommendations for implementation

- Answer the core research question: What metadata is most relevant when working with software assets?

Audience

This workshop is particularly relevant to the following communities:

- OSPO and Open Source Programme Managers
- Research Software and Open Science practitioners
- Metadata and infrastructure stakeholders
- Anyone involved in governance, monitoring, or reporting of open source assets

2. Metadata Prioritisation

Participants voted to surface the metadata properties most important to their workflows. Each participant had 5 Absolute Priority votes, 8 Important votes, and 12 Secondary votes to distribute across the properties.

Voting Results: Full Ranked Table

Properties are listed in descending order of absolute priority, then total votes.

Property	Absolute Priority	Important	Secondary	Total	OSPO Usage
name	7	1	0	8	identifying
licenses	6	2	0	8	compliance
identifier	4	2	0	6	identifying
author	3	3	0	6	identifying
funding (specific grant)	3	1	2	6	reporting
funder	3	1	0	4	reporting
code repo url	2	3	0	5	identifying, using
programming language	2	2	2	6	reporting, using
last modification date	2	2	1	5	reporting, using
software requirements	1	5	1	7	using
hardware requirements	1	2	0	3	using
version	1	2	2	5	using
development status	1	4	0	5	reporting, using
reference publication	1	4	2	7	reporting
maintainer	1	2	2	5	reporting, using
producer	1	0	1	2	reporting
creation date	1	0	3	4	reporting
contact point	0	4	3	7	using
keywords	0	3	2	5	identifying
features list	0	3	1	4	identifying, using
download url	0	3	0	3	using
citation	0	2	4	6	reporting

Property	Absolute Priority	Important	Secondary	Total	OSPO Usage
swhid	0	2	0	2	identifying
contributor	0	2	3	5	identifying, reporting
publication date	0	2	2	4	—
is accessible for free	0	2	0	2	using
forks	0	1	3	4	reporting
published on (platform)	0	1	3	4	using
application category	0	1	2	3	identifying, reporting
alternate name	0	1	1	2	identifying
copyright notice	0	1	1	2	compliance
forked from	0	1	1	2	reporting
supporting data	0	1	0	1	reporting
is source code of	0	1	0	1	identifying
issue tracker	0	1	0	1	using
origin url	0	1	0	1	identifying
same as	0	1	0	1	identifying
OS	0	0	4	4	using
likes	0	0	4	4	reporting
CI service	0	0	3	3	using
release notes	0	0	3	3	using
sponsor	0	0	3	3	reporting
related link	0	0	2	2	reporting
build instructions	0	0	1	1	using
package size	0	0	1	1	using
provider	0	0	1	1	reporting
copyright year	0	0	1	1	compliance
followers	0	0	1	1	reporting

Participant-Added Properties

Two additional properties were contributed during the activity:

Property	Absolute Priority	Important	Secondary	Total	OSPO Usage
documentation url	0	0	1	1	—
reference dataset / research outputs	0	1	0	1	—

Properties Receiving No Votes

The following 15 properties received no votes from participants:

- editor
- copyright holder
- total items
- position
- is part of
- credit text
- permissions
- memory requirements
- processor requirements
- storage requirements
- software suggestions
- file format
- encoding
- readme url
- install url

Key Discussion Points

Documentation URL: Multiple documentation sources should be accounted for, as they are not always up to date.

Reference dataset: Linking research publications, code, and data was identified as a useful addition.

Data quality concern: Participants raised concerns about ambiguous, obsolete, or unreliable properties. A recurring sentiment was that no data is better than bad data.

Preliminary Analysis

Name, licenses, and identifier emerged as the most important properties. The strong showing of the identifier was a notable finding. Funding-related and relational properties came next: funder, funding, reference publication, and software requirements.

Design Solutions: Brainstorming

The following approaches were discussed for surfacing metadata in the dashboard interface:

- Show only the top 3 properties in the list view
- Surface the next tier of properties at the top of the full asset view
- Dynamically surface properties on demand:
for example, allowing users to search for properties in the code and have them highlighted by the dashboard

3. Annotations Activity

Participants were invited to add and group possible annotations for software assets. The activity generated less discussion than anticipated, but produced a rich set of suggested annotations.

A significant observation from this activity: many of the suggested annotations are theoretically retrievable from code. This may reflect either limited awareness of existing metadata fields or a perception that such data is too often absent or unreliable in practice.

3.1 Funding

Proposed Annotation	Possible Metadata Mapping
Whether funding is active or past	–
Funding projects (DOI), grant IDs	funding
Related funding (grants, gifts, etc.)	funding
Funding sources	funding, funder

3.2 Impact Measures

Proposed Annotation	Possible Metadata Mapping
How to cite	citation.cff
Works that cite the software asset / cited by	related link? reference publication?
Software requirements	software requirements
Hardware requirements	hardware requirements
"Real world" dependencies (e.g. lab equipment depends on this software)	–
Related PIDs (publications, other research products)	reference publication, supporting data, related link

3.3 Relationship to Institution

Proposed Annotation	Possible Metadata Mapping
Institution uses	–
Institution contributes	–
Institution created	–

3.4 Development / Community Activity

Proposed Annotation	Possible Metadata Mapping
Development status, project status	development / project status
Maturity / state of development / development dynamics	aggregated data
Archived	development status
Is the project accepting contributions?	–
Last updated date	last modification date
Number of issues open / closed	from issue tracker
Forks	forks
Number of contributors	aggregated from forge?

3.5 Identifying Information

Proposed Annotation	Possible Metadata Mapping
Forked from	forked from
Description	description

Proposed Annotation	Possible Metadata Mapping
Keywords	keywords
Code repository URL	code repository url

3.6 Internal Profile

Proposed Annotation	Possible Metadata Mapping
Partner institutions; co-authoring / co-managing institutions	–
University affiliation for identified leads (faculty, PhD, RSE/staff, etc.)	–
University home (college / school / department / lab)	–
Researcher	–
Research team	–
External partners	–

3.7 Other

Proposed Annotation	Possible Metadata Mapping
Licenses	license
Maintainer	maintainer
Programming language	programming language
Academic field(s)	–
Is this an educational tool? An analytical tool?	–
Transfer action if exists	–

Preliminary Analysis

Most proposed annotations can be mapped to automatically retrievable information. The dashboard should encourage OSPOs to enforce best practices for filling these out in codemeta or other intrinsic metadata sources. Some fields (description, keywords) could be mirrored locally.

Annotations without a clear metadata mapping – likely requiring manual OSPO input – include:

- Status of funding (active or past)
- Real-world dependencies
- Accepting contributions
- Partners and external collaborators
- Researcher and research team identifiers
- Institutional department / lab affiliation
- Relationship between institution and asset
- Academic field(s)
- Educational / analytical tool flags

Some of this information could reference persons or organisations by unique identifiers (e.g. ORCID). Other items are purely contextual with no clear hierarchy, supporting the case for a flat annotation architecture.

⚠ Risk

Local annotations appear important to OSPOs in contexts where intrinsic metadata is absent or unreliable. There is a risk that OSPOs fill missing core information via annotations rather than enforcing best practices upstream.

💡 Implication for design

The growing importance of annotations supports making them searchable and usable as filters – though this becomes more complex with a flat tagging architecture.

⚠ Warning

The quality of the information is important to OSPOs but difficult to guarantee: intrinsic metadata is frequently absent, outdated, or unreliable in practice. A recurring sentiment among participants was that **no data is better than bad data**. The dashboard should make data gaps visible rather than silently omitting them, and actively encourage upstream best practices rather than allowing annotations to become a workaround for missing core metadata.

4. Open Questions

The workshop surfaced several unresolved questions that will inform further design and development work:

Q 1	Surfacing gaps vs. silently omitting properties: what is the right default?
Q 2	Highlighting quality issues could help enforce best practices, but may create noise.
Q 3	Risk of duplication or contradictory data between intrinsic metadata and OSPO-added annotations.

5. Next Steps

Based on workshop outcomes, the following directions are proposed for the OSPO-RADAR dashboard:

- Prioritise name, licenses, and identifier as core displayed properties in the list view
- Design a layered metadata display: top 3 in list view, expanded set in full asset view
- Investigate demand-driven surfacing of metadata properties (search + highlight in code)
- Develop an annotation architecture with searchability and filter support
- Encourage codemeta best practices to reduce reliance on manual annotation for core fields
- Map ORCID and ROR identifiers to relevant annotation fields (researchers, institutions)
- Further research on handling missing or ambiguous metadata gracefully

Annex A: Metadata Prioritisation Activity

Annex B: Annotation activity

